

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B288
Date: 28 April 2007
Take Off 13:15:39 20:06:25
Landing: 18:32:24 21:33:49
Flight Time 5h16m45 1h27m24

Campaign: IASI – METOP and AQUA overpass

Operating Area: Oklahoma ARM site

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	MARSS / Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14	Neph	DaveTiddeman	Met Office
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B288 Track 28-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B288
 Date: 28th April 2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: ARM site Oklahoma

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
125915		Start-Up	-.18 kft	179	29'36.28N 95'10.06W
131021		ASP	-.18 kft	063	Open
131539		T/O	-.20 kft	179	
134813		note	26.0 kft	335	weak contrails
134813		Tapes	26.0 kft	335	Tapes started DFC & RFC
135302		Note	26.0 kft	338	Contrails stopped
141710		Tapes	26.0 kft	341	RFC switched to UFC
141711	144050	Profile 1	26.0 - 4.7 kft	341	
144103		QNH	4.7 kft	349	1024
144309	144545	Profile 1	4.7 - 2.5 kft	348	
144554	151218	Run 1	2.4 kft	000	
145951		note	2.5 kft	358	Centre Point
151945		Tapes	6.5 kft	186	Changed
151551	153610	Profile 2	2.5 - 24.0 kft	186	
154119	155803	Profile 2	24.0 - 33.0 kft	353	Point SOUTH
160228		Sonde 1	33.1 kft	118	
160413		Sonde 2	33.0 kft	182	
160228	161656	Run 2.1	33.0 kft	190	
160607		Sonde 3	33.0 kft	189	
160806		Sonde 4	33.0 kft	181	
161620		Sonde 5	33.0 kft	180	
162417		Sonde 6	33.1 kft	016	
162417	164102	Run 2.2	33.0 kft	011	
162714		Sonde 7	33.0 kft	000	
163008		Sonde 8	33.0 kft	359	
163406		Sonde 9	33.0 kft	358	
163824		Sonde 10	33.0 kft	358	
164140		note	33.1 kft	248	Contrails at end of run
165203		Tapes	29.4 kft	210	Changed
164800	165750	Profile 3	33.0 - 20.1 kft	210	
170158	171039	Profile 3	20.1 - 5.8 kft	354	
171326	172138	Run 3	5.7 kft	173	
172138	172527	Profile 3	5.3 - 2.0 kft	177	
172527	172822	Run 4.1	2.0 kft	180	
173057	175526	Run 4.2	2.0 kft	005	
175744	181954	Run 4.3	2.0 kft	188	
183224		Land	0.97 kft	359	Will Rogers, Oklahoma
183450		ASP	1.00 kft	359	Closed
195206		Stop/refuel	1.0 kft	180	35'24.05N 97'36.16W
195904		ASP	1.0 kft	180	Open
195932		Tapes	1.0 kft	180	Changed
200625		T/O	0.99 kft	000	
201204	201436	Profile 4	8.7 - 6.7 kft	150	
201436	202041	Run 5	6.8 - 6.7 kft	151	
202042	202124	Profile 5	6.7 - 6.3 kft	146	
202124	202612	Run 6	6.3 - 6.4 kft	146	
202613	203608	Profile 6	6.4 - 15.0 kft	215	
213349		Land	-.15 kft	174	
213545		ASP	-.14 kft	255	Closed
213751		Shutdown	-.14 kft	179	29'36.28N 95'10.06W

B288 Track 28-APR-07

Sortie Brief – Oklahoma

Flight B288

Sat 28th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Stuart Newman

Briefing: 0615L = 1115Z

Take off: 0815L = 1315Z

Landing: 1345L = 1845Z

Satellite overpass = 1609Z

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite in the vicinity of the ARM site coordinated with the overpass.

Location: In vicinity of ARM instrument site located near Lamont, Oklahoma (central facility coordinates 36°37' N, 97°30' W)

Weather conditions: Clear skies or broken clouds.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over Oklahoma

Fixed point STH: (35°50' N, 97°36' W)

Fixed point NTH: (37°20'N, 97° 35'W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to Oklahoma point STH to arrive at minimum altitude e.g. 2700ft (90 mins)
2. SLR from STH to NTH at 2700ft (25 mins)
3. Profile from NTH to STH from 2700ft to maximum altitude, e.g. FL280 (30 mins)
4. SLR from STH to NTH at FL280 dropping sondes (see below) (20 mins)
5. SLR from NTH to STH at FL280 dropping sondes (20 mins) – overpass occurs during this run at **1609Z**
6. Profile from STH to NTH from FL280 to 2700ft (30 mins)
7. SLR from NTH to STH at 2700ft (25 mins)
8. Transit back to Houston (90 mins; total 330 mins)

Drop sonde pattern: aim is to launch sondes with good coverage along the sub-satellite track with particular density at the overpass time. Times below are approximate based on starting Run 2.2 at 1600Z.

Satellite overpass – 1609Z

<i>Dropsonde launch:</i>	<i>Time Z</i>	<i>Time relative to overpass (mins)</i>
Run 2.1		
#1	1539	T-30
#2	1543	T-26
#3	1547	T-22
#4	1551	T-18
Run 2.2		
#5	1600	T-9
#6	1602	T-7
#7	1605	T-4
#8	1607	T-2
#9	1615	T+6
#10	1618	T+9

ARIES operations

During 1st low level run, mainly NADIR with short ZEN view

During overpass run all NADIR

During other high level run mainly NADIR with short Zenith

During 2nd low level run mix of NADIR and ZEN

Cameras

Upward and downward facing unless otherwise stated

18:30

Sortie Brief - Oklahoma

Flight B288

Sat 28th April 2007 ³⁰⁵ ₁₂₇₃ 2

Mission Scientist: Stuart Newman

Briefing: 0615L = 1115Z

Take off: 0815L = 1315Z

Landing: 1345L = 1845Z

Satellite overpass = 1609Z - 11:09L

SL
TAKE OFF - 13:15:39
LANDING - 18:32:24
T/O
20M of LND - 20:06:25
Newman approx 21:33:45
0.8°C ↑
0.5°C ↑

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite in the vicinity of the ARM site coordinated with the overpass.

Location: In vicinity of ARM instrument site located near Lamont, Oklahoma (central facility coordinates 36°37' N, 97°30' W)

Weather conditions: Clear skies or broken clouds.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys ⇒ 9 1/2

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over Oklahoma

Fixed point STH: (35°50' N, 97°36' W)

Fixed point NTH: (37°20' N, 97° 35' W)

Will Rogers Refuel to work across 34 32 N 97 10 W low fuel warn

05:15

1. Take off from Houston and transit to Oklahoma point STH to arrive at minimum altitude e.g. 2700ft (90 mins)
- P1 R1 2. SLR from STH to NTH at 2700ft (25 mins)
- R1 3. Profile from NTH to STH from 2700ft to maximum altitude, e.g. FL280 (30 mins)
- R2 4. SLR from STH to NTH at FL280 dropping sondes (see below) (20 mins)
- R3 5. SLR from NTH to STH at FL280 dropping sondes (20 mins) - overpass occurs during this run at 1609Z
- P2 R4 6. Profile from STH to NTH from FL280 to 2700ft (30 mins)
- R4 7. SLR from NTH to STH at 2700ft (25 mins)
8. Transit back to Houston (90 mins; total 330 mins)

Beats on @ 16.5kft

Run about CO2

Run 1

Newman Calc no good.

PS Wt 20K 6K

16:34
16:39

- START CAMS
RETRACT BBR cap off @ 18000ft
CAL HIEMAN! Am
• Arrived on @ 23000ft my prompt
15:04 8ms
15:07
- HAD TO DO CAL @ end of Run cos forgot!!
 - 8kft DA back to AVAPS.

Mission scientist's debrief for JAIVEx flight B288 on 28 April 2007

S. M. Newman

Summary:

Good clear sky satellite validation case with only small high cloud amounts.
Successful sortie which exploited near-perfect clear sky conditions over Oklahoma.
Opportunistic interception of oil fire plume.
Good contrails flight.

This flight was in conjunction with a MetOp satellite overpass over the Oklahoma ARM site and included an opportunistic oil refinery fire interception. FAAM 146 flew a north-south track passing just west of the ARM central facility while NASA WB-57 flew at 55,000 feet in a racetrack pattern.

During the transit intermittent contrails were encountered which were monitored on the rearward facing camera. The FAAM 146 commenced with a low level run north at 2700 feet in completely clear sky conditions, which changed slightly to wisps of high cloud at the northern end of the run. A profile climb managed to reach FL330, followed by two straight and level runs at this altitude coinciding with the MetOp overpass. A total of ten dropsondes were launched from high level, with the first four in the air at the overpass time. Slightly more high cloud was present at the northern end by the time the high level legs were completed.

A decision was made to refuel at Will Rogers Oklahoma City in order to fit in two more runs at 2,300 feet (again, clear at southern end) and exploit the opportunity to sample the oil refinery smoke plume which had resulted from a lightning strike. After take-off the fire was easily spotted (dark smoke capped by the inversion at the top of the boundary layer) and the smoke was sampled at 6,500 feet. CNC and nephelometer showed large signals whereas CO was relatively unaffected. AMS saw organics while 2DC reported 400 micron particles shaped like "moons". As with Buncefield this opportunistic sortie should be interesting for studies of oil fire pollutants.

After landing the interferometers ARIES (on the stationary FAAM 146) and Scanning-HIS (on the pan) operating looking in the zenith at the clear sky. Unfortunately it later transpired that the S-HIS data recording was corrupted, and so no intercomparison could be made.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN JAIVEX OKLAHOMA

Flight No **B.288**
FAAM © 2004

Date **28/4/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1315	TAKE-OFF				
1331	Transit	FL232	329	30°18' 95°30'	Extensive Sc below on transit
1340	"	FL260	328	31°, 95°50'	PCASP ~ 150 last 10 mins
1347					Just contrailing now
134750					Intermittent contrailing CAMERAS REAR
134950					MARSS notes correlation between channel 18 and contrailing
135130	Transit	FL260	321	31°54' 96°12'	FWVS and GE showing similar w.v. structure
ENGINE SETTINGS					N1 86.9 86.8 86.7 86.9
					TGT 70.5 69.3 67.6 71.5
					N2 87.8 88.3 87.7 87.7
					FF/FU S.1 S.0 S.0 S.2
1414	Transit	FL260	341	33°42' 96°50'	Scattered Cu below, largely clear
141711	P ↓	FL260 ↓	341		Smoke below, but too far below to intercept, fire?
1426	"	FL188	346	34°36' 97°12'	Clear apart from sig. haze
					[34°32' N 97°10' W pos. of fire source]
1439	"	25500'	348	35°30' 97°30'	WB-57: problems with NAST, SHIS ok
144050	Interr-upt	5000'	349	35°30' 97°30'	Hold at 5000'; clear at all levels
144309	Recommence	5000' ↓	348	35°42' 97°30'	Boundary layer on desert ≈ 6000ft from RH
144545	End P1	2700'			
144554	RI	"	359	35°48' 97°36'	Clear as a bell, over patchwork fields
1454	"	"	359	36°18' 97°36'	Still clear, few wisps high cloud to N
1457	"	"			55,500 ft WB-57
145940	"	"	358	36°36' 97°36'	Centre point
1503					MARSS: moistening at high level consistent with wisps high cloud
1510	"	"	358	37°19' 97°30'	Near N. pt, wispy high level cloud

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.288**
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **28/4/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
151218	End R1				Still clear apart from wisps high cloud
151551	Start P2	2700' ↑	187	37°12', 9730	Heading south
1522		8800'	182	36°48', 9750	~ 500 PCASP consistent ^{→ neatly correlates at +}
153610	inter-upt	FL240			Big peak in ozone at this altitude, anticorrelation with CO? T/φ gram shows v. dry atmosphere
154119	Resume	FL240 ↑	354	35°42', 9750	Return profile to North
1545					O ₃ returns to < 50, peak was well-defined layer RD-93 dropsondes
1553		FL323 ↑	358	36°42', 9730	Still high cloud ahead to northern end
160228	START OF RUN NOT STR. + LEVEL				Sonde #1 160228 not quite on track, still turning
					#2 160413
1605			189		STRA Straight level now back on track
					#3 160607
					#4 160806
1609	dropsonde altitudes are:				3707m, 5058m, 6872m, 8870m
1612	R2.1	FL330	183	97°36', 366'	Clear at S. end of run
					#5 161620
161656	End R2.1				
162417	R2.2	FL330	180	35°34', 9736	#6 162417 on return run
					#7 162714 → profile looks clear
					#8 163008
					#9 163406
					#10 163824
164107					Start contrailing at end of Run coinciding with brief peak in dew pt. ~1641

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.288**
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 Date **28/4/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
164800	P3 ↓	FL330 ↓	199	37°0', 97°30'	Some high cloud at this northern end
165425	"	FL243	183	36°24', 97°36'	Dry, T -26°C, Td -41°C Wind 15ms ² /307
165750	Interr- upt	FL200	184	36°6', 97°56'	Brief peak in CO
		FL200 ↓	002		
171039	Interr- upt	6000'			More wisps high cloud above
171326	R3	6000'	176	36°24', 97°30'	Ad-hoc run while waiting for permission to land + refuel at Will Rogers
172138	Profile 3 resume	6000 ↓	182	36°12', 97°30'	
172527	End	2300'			
end 172822	Start R4.1	"	181		Clear sky above
173057	R4.2	2300'	0		QC spike
1742	"	"	0	36°50', 97°30'	Few wisps high cloud above
1748		"			MARS: variations of 20K in channels sensitive to UTWV
175526	end R4.2	"			
175744	R4.3	"	188		
1807	"				AMES: "clear above"
1819	"				Largely clear above
181954	end R4.3				
	Land				Land at Oklahoma Will Rogers Refuel
2005	T/O	—————→			T/O from Will Rogers
2010					Fire burning clearly visible
201204	P4				Descent to 7000' to intercept plume
2014					Run into plume
					Smoke line capped inversion spread out in layer near 7000ft
2021					Descent to 6500', better intercept
202130					Into smoke S, 6,000 PCASP

Lightning strike on oil refinery

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B288 **T/O:** 131539
Date of flight: 28 APRIL 2007 **Land:** 213349

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	No	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B287_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	<p>yes</p> <p>Only 2dc</p>	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =a</p> <p>Start = 131539 End = 213349</p> <p>Time data processed to = 212014 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat yes</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>ii). exit</p>	<p>yes</p>	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	<p>yes</p>	<p>Mfda - mfdb</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>No nevz broken</p>	<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B288
Date of flight: 28 APRIL 2007

T/O: 131539
Land: 213349

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	yes	Min size =2 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	yes	Mfdb - mfdc
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	yes	Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B288	Date	28 Apr 2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, land</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
16:02:30	1	Launch	261.50 -50.30 56.02 342.30 11.90 -16.50 -97.647800 37.131300 10069.70
16:14:08	1	land	982.4799.00 999.00 351.65 1.68 -5.40 -97.614223 37.066917 99999.00
16:04:12	2	Launch	261.70 -50.30 58.09 322.70 16.00 -15.90 -97.538900 36.976700 10065.70
16:15:42	2	land	982.09 18.96 53.25 274.88 2.40 - 2.01 -97.505631 36.914176 8.12
16:06:09	3	Launch	261.50 -50.40 62.42 330.10 16.20 -16.80 -97.573600 36.769400 10069.40
16:17:40	3	land	987.14 19.52 50.76 264.13 2.79 -0.08 -97.540775 36.707624 -33.35
16:08:09	4	Launch	261.70 -50.30 64.74 339.90 15.40 -18.20 -97.592700 36.562600 10064.50
16:19:52	4	land	985.52 19.77 51.06 327.49 2.68 -11.62 -97.560722 36.500401 -21.10 GPS pretty much dropped out at low level
16:16:24	5	Launch	261.60 -50.10 51.51 344.30 12.00 -17.20 -97.595700 35.715100 10068.20
16:27:48	5	land	983.49 18.97 58.18 357.15 2.49 -11.85 -97.569920 35.658800 -20.67
16:24:33	6	Launch	261.60 -50.10 49.05 352.00 21.50 -16.70 -97.610600 35.856800 10067.20
16:35:39	6	land	986.04 20.03 49.53 5.04 2.69 -11.21 -97.593998 35.774367 -18.12
16:27:18	7	Launch	261.60 -50.10 54.08 355.00 21.40 -16.30 -97.597400 36.105800 10066.90
16:41:38	7	land	989.20 23.11 40.73 147.23 0.02 0.01 -97.568451 36.042678 -59.64
16:30:09	8	Launch	261.60 -50.30 50.19 349.20 21.20 -16.90 -97.594400 36.362100 10066.90
16:41:47	8	land	981.55 20.30 47.21 355.89 3.95 -0.06 -97.564542 36.303267 8.85
16:34:18	9	Launch	261.70 -50.20 54.05 345.60 21.20 -17.00 -97.590000 36.731600 10066.20
16:45:41	9	land	987.98 20.99 999.00 349.62 3.76 0.01 -97.558739 36.658133 -32.35 Occ loss of GPS below approx 10000'
163827	10	Launch	261.80 -50.00 58.19 344.00 20.20 -16.80 -97.586000 37.100900 10062.10
164959	10	land	983.41 20.24 46.88 257.67 3.00 -11.54 -97.550963 37.038266 99999.00 telemetry dropouts (GPS & PTU) below about 3000' prob due to start of descent

B288 CVI log

4/28/07	1:37:30 PM	zero 26kft
4/28/07	3:36:48 PM	zero 24kft
4/28/07	3:36:54 PM	zero 24kft
4/28/07	3:52:54 PM	zero 31kft
4/28/07	4:39:29 PM	zero 33kft
4/28/07	4:59:15 PM	zero 20kft
4/28/07	6:41:05 PM	184000 zeroed on ground @ Oklahoma
4/28/07	7:30:32 PM	19301900 zeroed on ground @ Oklahoma
4/28/07	8:11:39 PM	zero at 2.5KM
4/28/07	8:13:39 PM	zero at 2.2km
4/28/07	8:15:26 PM	zero at 7000ft

B288_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

11:45:44.37 --- - - - -
11:45:44.37 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:45:44.37 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                               tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:45:44.37 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B288
11:45:44.37 --- - - - -
11:46:03.16 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
11:46:06.75 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
11:46:09.15 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
11:46:12.28 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:46:16.62 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:46:20.59 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:46:24.56 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:47:06.84 SWS - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
11:47:10.55 SWS - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
11:47:14.97 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
11:47:18.57 USH - - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
11:47:21.85 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
11:47:25.15 LSH - - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
11:47:36.37 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:36.38 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:36.38 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:42.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:42.80 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:42.85 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:47.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:48.43 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:48.63 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:53.08 SWS - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
11:47:56.69 SWS - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
11:48:02.81 USH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
11:48:06.71 USH - - - 990 - NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
11:48:10.44 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
11:48:13.43 LSH - - - 990 - NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
11:48:15.48 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:48:15.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:48:16.06 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:48:23.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:48:25.83 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:48:26.39 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:50:28.01 --- - - - - *** Time set not working as with B282 - turns
                               out hub breaker had been pulled
11:50:51.76 --- - - - - *** hub breaker re-made and all is good
12:39:10.29 USH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
12:39:15.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:15.44 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:15.50 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:23.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:25.83 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:27.04 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:28.25 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:45:10.85 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
12:45:16.39 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:45:26.73 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:02:26.98 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:02:27.01 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:02:27.69 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:02:35.11 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:02:37.32 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:02:38.03 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:13.55 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:13.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:13.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:21.98 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:23.88 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:24.17 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:23:33.28 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.

```

13:23:41.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:45.68	USH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
13:23:49.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:50.48	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
13:23:58.00	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 400ms.
13:24:05.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:05.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:05.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:13.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:15.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:16.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:20.14	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
13:39:28.00	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
13:39:31.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:31.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:31.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:39.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:41.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:41.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:25.04	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
13:42:29.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:39.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:05.59	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
13:45:10.36	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
13:45:18.07	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
13:45:26.26	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
13:45:30.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:30.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:31.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:38.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:41.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:41.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:10.90	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:52:38.39	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:52:43.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:43.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:44.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:51.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:54.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:54.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:44.03	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
13:54:51.11	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
13:54:56.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:04.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:28.84	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
14:02:34.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:35.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:35.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:43.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:44.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:45.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:21.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:21.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:21.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:29.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:31.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:32.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:12:53.86	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
14:13:01.75	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
14:13:06.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:09.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:14.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:19.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:24.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:24.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:24.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:32.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:34.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:35.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:20:37.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:12.56	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
14:21:23.40	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
14:21:26.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:26.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:26.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:34.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:36.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:36.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:17.60	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:22:20.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:25.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:39.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:40.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:40.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:45.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:50.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:50.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:16.01	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:33:19.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:27.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:21.76	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
14:35:25.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:30.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:47.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:47.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:47.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:52.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:55.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:58.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:41.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:42.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:42.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:47.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:50.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:52.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:59.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1
14:51:08.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:09.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:09.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:14.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:16.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:19.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:27.04	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
14:51:30.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:38.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:08.58	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:53:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:53:19.00	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:53:22.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:22.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:23.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:30.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:30.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:33.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:06.06	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
14:55:11.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:21.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:44.97	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:56:12.54	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
14:56:23.57	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
14:56:28.79	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:56:32.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:33.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:33.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:37.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:41.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:43.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:35.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:01:35.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:35.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:39.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:43.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:45.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:03.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:06:09.08	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:06:14.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:14.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:14.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:22.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:22.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:24.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:55.85	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:08:59.71	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
15:09:05.16	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
15:09:08.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:08.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:08.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:16.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:19.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:24.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1
15:32:48.71	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
15:32:53.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:53.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:53.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:32:57.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:01.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:03.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:12.35	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:45:16.38	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
15:45:21.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:21.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:21.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:22.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:26.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:26.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:32.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:36.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:41.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:45:46.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:25.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:25.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:25.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:29.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:29.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:35.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:25.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:26.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:26.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:30.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:30.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:36.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:51.39	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
16:03:04.23	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:03:09.73	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
16:03:14.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:15.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:15.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:20.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:23.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:25.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:40.38	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:04:45.41	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
16:04:47.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:53.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:12.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2 (though still turning) coincident with first sonde drop

```

16:06:45.08 --- - - - *** run 2 started 160228
16:07:36.94 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
16:07:40.72 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:07:51.07 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:08:02.96 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:08:06.71 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:08:15.54 SWS - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
16:08:17.18 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:08:18.78 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:08:24.21 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:08:52.99 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:08:53.12 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:08:53.79 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:08:58.42 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:08:58.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:09:04.12 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:09:31.24 SWS - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
16:09:33.06 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:09:37.49 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:14:00.34 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:14:00.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:14:01.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:14:04.78 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:14:05.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:14:11.48 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:17:10.99 --- - - - - *** end of run 2 161656
16:19:49.37 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:19:49.75 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:19:50.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:19:54.18 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:19:55.33 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:20:00.36 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:24:57.46 --- - - - - *** start of run2.2 still in turn 162427
16:25:03.63 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:25:04.11 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:25:04.43 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:25:08.55 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:25:09.10 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:25:14.77 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:26:54.29 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:26:59.80 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:27:02.84 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:27:13.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:31:23.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:31:23.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:31:23.59 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:31:27.88 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:31:29.08 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:31:34.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:34:59.65 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
16:35:04.75 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
16:35:08.07 SWS - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
16:35:10.81 SWS - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:35:17.40 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:35:17.49 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:35:17.64 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:35:23.24 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:35:25.54 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:35:27.74 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:37:47.06 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
16:37:51.34 SWS - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
16:37:54.80 SWS - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
16:37:59.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:37:59.67 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:37:59.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:38:04.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:38:05.09 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:38:10.45 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:40:47.80 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.

```

16:40:49.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:53.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:04.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:41:12.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:41:12.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:41:13.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:41:17.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:18.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:23.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:24.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:24.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:24.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:28.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:29.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:34.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:32.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:57:32.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:57:33.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:57:37.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:38.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:43.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:00:59.50	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
17:01:04.42	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:01:08.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:01:09.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:01:09.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:01:13.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:14.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:01:19.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:18.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:19.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:19.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:23.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:23.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:29.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:48.02	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
17:06:52.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:02.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:09:21.06	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
17:09:27.41	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
17:09:31.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:09:36.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:02.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:13:02.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:13:02.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:13:07.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:08.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:13.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:12.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:13.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:13.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:17.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:18.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:23.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:36.79	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
17:20:40.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:51.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:23:53.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:23:53.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:23:54.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:23:58.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:23:59.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:05.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:39.34	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:25:41.77	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:26:00.42	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
17:26:07.03	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:26:27.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:26:27.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

17:26:28.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:26:32.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:33.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:38.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:41.49	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:26:46.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:26:54.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:07.32	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:28:13.41	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
17:28:18.26	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
17:28:22.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:22.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:23.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:26.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:27.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:33.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:59.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:59.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:59.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:02.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:04.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:09.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:57.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:58.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:58.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:01.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:37:03.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:37:09.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:12.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:13.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:13.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:16.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:18.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:23.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:47:48.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:49.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:49.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:52.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:47:54.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:47:59.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:48.61	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:48:52.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:03.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:51.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:51.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:52.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:55.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:57.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:53:02.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:55:27.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:55:27.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:55:27.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:55:30.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:55:33.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:55:38.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:25.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 4.2 175526
17:57:00.35	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:57:11.76	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
17:57:32.00	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
17:57:40.28	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
17:57:46.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:46.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:46.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:51.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:53.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:56.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:15.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 4.3 175744
17:58:45.43	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
17:58:52.64	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.

17:58:58.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:06.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:28.10	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:59:33.79	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:59:41.03	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:59:42.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:42.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:43.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:43.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:48.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:51.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:59:53.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:56.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:00:25.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** a little bouncy so having difficulty with mouse pad
18:01:20.31	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:01:24.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:34.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:57.81	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:02:03.33	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:02:07.91	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
18:02:16.05	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
18:02:21.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:22.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:22.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:26.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:27.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:32.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:15.30	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
18:03:18.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:03:22.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:49.10	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
18:04:02.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:06.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:26.28	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
18:04:33.47	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
18:04:40.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:50.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:05:36.55	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:05:51.24	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
18:05:55.67	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
18:06:08.53	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
18:06:11.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:12.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:12.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:17.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:20.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:22.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:34.48	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
18:06:40.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:48.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:06.57	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:07:10.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:20.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:08:38.97	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:08:43.69	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
18:08:48.83	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
18:08:55.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:08:56.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:08:56.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:09:00.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:09:01.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:09:06.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:07.90	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:11:10.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:21.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:38.73	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:11:42.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:53.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:12:22.28	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:12:29.16	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
18:12:32.74	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
18:12:36.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:36.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:37.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:41.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:45.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:47.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:13:46.48	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
18:13:48.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:56.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:15.35	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:15:20.08	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
18:15:25.14	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
18:15:29.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:29.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:29.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:34.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:35.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:15:40.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:39.76	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:18:44.71	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
18:18:48.66	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
18:18:54.64	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
18:18:58.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:58.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:58.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:59.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:19:04.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:06.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:09.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:19:12.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:59.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:20:12.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:13.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:18.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:21.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:23.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:37:26.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:37:28.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:37:30.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:37:38.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:37:40.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B288 page 1 of

Date: 28/04/07 Operator(s): Joss Res: 1 Gain A: Z B: Z

Loc./Notes: IASI HOUSTON OKLAHOMA ARM SITE.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
074000		ASCI1	Housekeeping				started
124343	GRND		cal	clsd	7024	3108	
134350	Transit	FL260	cal	clsd	7030	3070	
134851	" "	" "	Zen	open	6926	3062	Clear above
134750	" "	" "	NW	clsd	7026	3049	
135204	" "	" "	cal	clsd	7028	3102	
144510	R1	1/60	cal	clsd	7074	3081	
144639	R1	600/1	NW	clsd	7076	3061	
145141	R1	1/60	cal	clsd	7083	3060	
145258	R1	300/1	Zen	open	7025	3052	Clear above
145533	R1	300/1	NW	clsd	7012	3180	
145811	R1	1/60	cal	clsd	7012	3145	
145929	R1	600/1	NW	clsd	7022	3102	
150436	R1	1/60	cal	clsd	7101	3108	
150556	R1	300/1	Zen	open	7016	3142	Clear above. Maybe wispy cirrus
150946	R1	300/1	NW	clsd	7060	3092	
151122	R1	1/60	cal	clsd	7087	3061	
160128	R2	1/60	cal	clsd	7055	3049	
160253	R2	600/1	NW	clsd	7092	3047	Clear below. <i>→ end 160622</i> Some minor cirrus @ start
160635	R2	1/60	cal	clsd	7074	3042	
160752	R2	600/1	NW	clsd	7046	3053	swirls overpass
161259	R2	1/60	cal	clsd	7073	3087	
161435	R2	600/1	NW	clsd			end 161930
161852	R2	1/60	cal	clsd	7064	3036	
162254	R?	1/60	cal	clsd	7065	3013	
162425	R2						
1625	ARIES failure						couldn't get EDH data, reloaded ARIES
162725	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7092	3769	
162835?	R2.2	600/1	NW	clsd	7092	3293	Clear below.
163841	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7077	3091	
163803	R2.2	300/1	Zen	open	7019	3021	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 3288

page 2 of

Date: 29/1/07

Operator(s): JCS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
163736	R2.2	300/1	Nav	clsd	7012	30.80	Clear below.
164011	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7064	30.63	HBB low
171714	R	1/60	beam open				
171714	R3?	1/60	cal	clsd	7064	30.48	
171842	R3	600/1	Nav	clsd	7085	30.37	end 172138
172138	R3	1/60	cal	clsd			
172202	R	1/60	cal	clsd	7085	30.85	
172425	.	1/60	cal	clsd	7079	30.45	
172552	R4.1	300/1	zen	open	7014	31.05	
172803	R4.1	300/1	Nav	clsd	7014	30.65	end 172846
172905	-	1/60	cal	clsd	7008	31.54	
173005	R4-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7087	30.56	
173213	R4-2	600/1	Nav	clsd	7090	30.66	stopped early
173402	R4-2	300/1	Nav	clsd	7074	30.29	stopped @ 104% of run !?
173646	R4-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7079	30.09	
173805	R4-2	600/1	Nav	clsd	709	30.96	
174311	R4-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7065	30.25	
174435	R4-2	600/1	Nav	clsd	7078	30.34	
174941	R4-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7082	31.02	
175102	R4-2	600/1	Nav	clsd	7085	30.52	end 175530
175345	R4-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7097	30.87	
175745	R4-3	1/60	cal	clsd	7093	30.81	
175906	R4-3	300/1	zen	open	7029	31.17	clear above
180141	R4-3	300/1	Nav	clsd	7087	32.4	
180441	R4-3	1/60	cal	clsd	7087	31.96	
180530	R4-3	300/1	zen	open	7063	31.83	
180820	R4-3	300/1	Nav	clsd	7096	33.45	
181050	R4-3	1/60	cal	clsd	709	33.64	
181206	R4-3	300/1	zen	open	7026	32.90	
181437	R4-3	300/1	Nav	clsd	7087	33.96	
181720	R4-4	1/60	cal	clsd	7101	33.37	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	28/04/07	Flight	B288	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	JAIVEX			
Departure	Ellington Field		Arrival	Ellington Field			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on			At time	11:33			
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	21.6°C	Ch	21.9°C	Ch18	21.5°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on			at time	08:14:05			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	292.7	Cold	291.4			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	11:33			
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software			at time				
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	12:45:39			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.52	Cold	294.10		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	1	31.83	39.41	39.50	41.66		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.288**.....

 Date **28/04/2007**.....

 Operator's name **D. TIDDEMAN**.....

 Page **1** of **2**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
14:47	Run 1	2700ft	12.0	32.1	28.9	A30°	10°	
14:52	"	"	12.0	31.1	55.4	A35°	30°	
14:55:20	"	"	12.0	32.1	64.7	A40°	35°	
14:58:40	"	"	12.8	33.1	75.2	A40°	40°	
15:06:50	"	"	12.2	34.4	41.3	A40°	16°	
15:11:10	"	"	12.2	33.1	73.2	A45°	40°	
15:12:18	"	"	12.2	33.1	81.0	A40°	45°	
15:19:49	Profile 2		10.7	19.1	43.0	A5°	20°	
15:33:29	"	2000ft	44.2	0.0	14.2	-	6°	Chiller off.
16:50:49			12.2	0.0	22.1	A5°	20°	Chiller on
17:16	Run 3	6000ft	12.7	16.5	21.3	A35°	5°	
17:25	Profile 3	>	14.2	36.0	65.1	A40°	35°	
17:32	Run 4?	2300ft	12.2	42.3	44.0	A40°	15°	
17:39	"	"	11.9	38.6	82.3	A45°	40°	
17:41	"	"	11.4	37.0	89.1	A8°	45°	
17:57	"	"	12.0	39.3	40.7	A40°	10°	
18:01	"	"	11.7	41.6	79.2	A40°	40°	
18:11	"	"	11.8	31.8	40.7	A40°	13°	
18:16:30	"	"	11.8	33.1	78.1	A45°	40°	

Flight:

B288

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 08/05/2007
18:37:18**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

29/04/2007 21:38:27

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B288

Date: 28 April 2007

Instruments

1. Not receiving SATCOM messages
2. Lower BBR not retracted till 16:09:00 on run 2.1
3. Lower BBR not retracted till 17:19 on run 3

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 28/04/07

Flight No: 6288

Pre-Flighter: JT/BW

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	J023
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
		<u>External</u>	BW	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	No photo
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	

<u>Avalon Checks</u>			<u>Signed</u>
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned <i>pending drying</i>	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied	
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)	MD'

Flight B288 15:58:16

Heading 358 deg Speed 366 knots Height 33.0kft Press 261mb

Lat 37°6.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 21 ms-1/ 347 deg 1.0.

Temp -50.27C Dewpoint -54.73C

From 15:15:52 to now

i73 - 1 23 av

0.9°C ↑

Current values			
PRESSURE HEIGHT	33.04	Kft	● All
CO MIXING RATIO	156.82	ppb	⊕
NEPH BLUE SP	2.79	m-1	⊕
NEPH GREEN SP	0.87	m-1	⊕
NEPH RED SP	1.1	m-1	⊕

7:40 9:40

ETA - 21:40

ft 250

x 3 2800 ppb spikes in Co.

Instrument
probs - Heenan Cab.
On 16 Mar 2007

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B288:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version with no missing logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647
Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk